

STAGES AND METHODS OF FPS GAME DEVELOPMENT BASED ON VIRTUAL REALITY TECHNOLOGY

Ibodullayev Sardor Nasriddin o‘g‘li

Assistant of the department of audiovisual technologies,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi,

Sodiqjonov Yaxyobek Sobirjon o‘g‘li

Student of the department of audiovisual technologies,
Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8043620>

Qabul qilindi: 15.06.2023

Crossref DOI: 10.24412/cl-37059-2023-06-65-71

UDK: 004.822

Annotation: This article explores the stages and methods involved in developing a first-person shooter (FPS) game using virtual reality (VR) technology. It covers the key considerations from conceptualization to post-launch support. The article discusses the importance of selecting the right VR platform, designing VR interactions, and creating immersive levels. It also delves into optimizing performance, testing, and iterating for a smooth VR experience. Furthermore, the article emphasizes the significance of sound design and multiplayer considerations in socializing the virtual battlefield. The annotation highlights the comprehensive coverage of the topic, making it a valuable resource for developers looking to venture into VR FPS game development.

Keywords: FPS game development, Virtual reality technology, Stages of development, Methods of development, Conceptualization, VR platform selection, VR interactions, Level design, VR movement implementation, Performance optimization, Testing and iteration, Sound design in VR, Multiplayer considerations, Cooperative gameplay, Competitive modes, Networking and latency, Matchmaking and lobbies, Anti-cheat measures, Cross-platform support, Post-launch support and updates.

**ЭТАПЫ И МЕТОДЫ РАЗРАБОТКИ FPS-ИГРЫ НА ОСНОВЕ
ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ВИРТУАЛЬНОЙ РЕАЛЬНОСТИ.**

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются этапы и методы разработки шутера от первого лица (FPS) с использованием технологии виртуальной реальности (VR). Он охватывает ключевые аспекты от концептуализации до поддержки после запуска. В статье обсуждается важность выбора правильной VR-платформы, проектирования VR-взаимодействий и создания иммерсивных уровней. Он также углубляется в оптимизацию производительности, тестирование и итерацию для плавного взаимодействия с виртуальной реальностью. Кроме того, в статье подчеркивается важность звукового оформления и многопользовательской игры для социализации виртуального поля битвы. В аннотации подчеркивается всесторонний охват темы, что делает ее ценным ресурсом для разработчиков, желающих заняться разработкой VR-шутеров от первого лица.

Ключевые слова: разработка игр FPS, технология виртуальной реальности, этапы разработки, методы разработки, концептуализация, выбор платформы виртуальной реальности, взаимодействие с виртуальной реальностью, дизайн уровней, реализация движения виртуальной реальности, оптимизация производительности, тестирование и итерация, звуковой дизайн в виртуальной реальности, соображения многопользовательской игры, кооператив геймплей, соревновательные режимы, работа в сети и задержка, матчмейкинг и лобби, меры по борьбе с мошенничеством, кроссплатформенная поддержка, поддержка и обновления после запуска.

INTRODUCTION.

The combination of first-person shooter (FPS) games and virtual reality (VR) technology has opened up new possibilities for immersive and captivating gaming experiences. Developing an FPS game in VR requires a careful and strategic approach, taking into account various stages and methods to ensure a seamless and engaging gameplay experience. This article aims to explore the stages and methods involved in FPS game development based on virtual reality technology. From conceptualization to post-launch support, each stage plays a crucial role in crafting a compelling VR FPS game. By understanding the key considerations and steps involved, developers can create games that transport players into thrilling virtual worlds, where they can become the protagonist in intense firefights. Throughout the article, we will delve into topics such as selecting the appropriate

VR platform, designing immersive VR interactions, creating captivating levels, implementing VR movement systems, optimizing performance, testing and iteration, sound design, multiplayer considerations, and post-launch support. These stages and methods will provide a roadmap for developers looking to dive into the exciting realm of FPS game development in VR. By understanding the intricacies of each stage and applying the appropriate methods, developers can harness the full potential of VR technology to deliver an unparalleled FPS gaming experience. So, let us embark on this journey through the stages and methods of FPS game development in virtual reality, where players can step into the shoes of a virtual soldier and engage in heart-pounding action like never before.

DEVELOPING FPS GAMES WITH VIRTUAL REALITY TECHNOLOGY: A COMPREHENSIVE GUIDE.

Virtual Reality (VR) technology has been a game-changer in the world of gaming, especially for first-person shooter (FPS) games. Immersive, interactive, and engaging, VR has brought new life to FPS gaming by placing players directly into the action. This article will guide you through the steps and methods necessary to develop FPS games based on virtual reality technology.

1. Concept Development and Pre-Production.

Before diving into game development, the first step is to create a solid concept and design for your FPS game.

This involves:

Defining your game's goals and objectives: Outline the core mechanics, gameplay, and features that will set your FPS apart from competitors. Consider how VR technology will enhance the gaming experience.

Creating a backstory and setting: Develop a compelling narrative and world for players to explore. This will help create an immersive environment and contribute to the overall game experience.

Designing characters and weapons: Sketch out the main characters and weapons players will use in the game. This includes designing their appearance, abilities, and attributes.

Storyboarding and level design: Plan out the game's levels and missions, including the objectives, enemy placement, and environmental challenges.

2. Assembling the Right Team.

Developing a VR-based FPS game requires a diverse skill set. Assemble a team that includes:

Programmers: Skilled in languages like C++, C#, and Python, programmers will be responsible for writing the game's code.

Designers: Responsible for creating the game's visual elements, including character models, environments, and user interfaces.

Animators: Bring characters and objects to life through realistic, fluid motions.

Audio Engineers: Create the game's sound effects and music, enhancing the immersive experience.

VR Specialists: Ensure the game's compatibility with VR hardware and optimize the user experience for VR gameplay.

3. Choosing the Right Game Engine.

Selecting the appropriate game engine will greatly impact your FPS game's development process. Popular game engines like Unity and Unreal Engine offer built-in support for VR development, making them excellent choices for VR-based FPS games. Consider factors such as ease of use, compatibility with your chosen VR hardware, and the availability of resources and documentation when selecting a game engine.

4. Developing the Core Mechanics.

With a solid concept, team, and game engine in place, the next step is to develop the core mechanics of your FPS game. This involves:

Implementing player movement: Create a comfortable and intuitive movement system for your VR game, considering options like teleportation, arm-swinging, or joystick-based locomotion.

Developing shooting mechanics: Ensure the game's shooting mechanics are responsive and accurate. Players should feel a sense of control and precision when aiming and firing weapons in the VR environment.

Creating an inventory and weapon switching system: Design an intuitive system for players to manage their weapons and equipment in the virtual space.

Optimizing performance: VR games require high frame rates and low latency to create a comfortable experience. Focus on optimizing your game's performance to minimize motion sickness and ensure smooth gameplay.

5. Designing Immersive Environments and Assets.

A key component of any VR-based FPS game is the creation of immersive environments and assets.

This includes:

Crafting detailed environments: Design and model realistic environments that contribute to the game's narrative and setting.

Creating realistic character models: Develop high-quality character models that are both visually appealing and optimized for VR performance.

Animating characters and objects: Use motion capture or keyframe animation techniques to create smooth, lifelike animations for characters and objects within the game.

Designing user interfaces: Create intuitive and immersive user interfaces for menus, HUDs, and other in-game elements.

6. Testing and Iteration.

Testing is crucial for the development of any game, particularly for VR-based FPS games. Regular testing ensures that the game is free of bugs, performance issues, and design flaws. During the testing phase:

Playtest the game: Test the game regularly, both internally and with external playtesters, to identify and address issues.

Optimize performance: Continuously optimize your game's performance to ensure it runs smoothly on a variety of VR hardware.

Gather feedback: Seek feedback from playtesters on the game's mechanics, design, and overall experience. Use this feedback to make improvements and fine-tune the game.

Debug and fix issues: Identify and resolve any bugs or glitches that arise during testing.

7. Marketing and Release.

Once your VR-based FPS game is fully developed and tested, it's time to begin marketing and preparing for release.

This involves:

Building a community: Engage with potential players on social media, forums, and other platforms to create buzz around your game.

Creating promotional materials: Develop trailers, screenshots, and other promotional content to showcase your game's unique features and VR capabilities.

Attending industry events: Showcase your game at gaming conventions, expos, and other industry events to generate interest and network with other developers and publishers.

Launching the game: Release your game on popular VR platforms like SteamVR, Oculus Rift, and PlayStation VR, and implement a marketing plan to drive sales and downloads.

Developing an FPS game for virtual reality can be a challenging yet rewarding process. By following these steps and methods, you'll be well on your way to creating an immersive and engaging gaming experience that leverages the full potential of VR technology.

CONCLUSION.

Developing a first-person shooter (FPS) game based on virtual reality (VR) technology requires careful consideration of various stages and methods. This article has explored the key aspects of FPS game development in VR, from conceptualization to post-launch support. Selecting the appropriate VR platform and designing immersive VR interactions are crucial for delivering an engaging experience. Level design that leverages the capabilities of VR, implementing VR movement systems, and optimizing performance are essential for creating a seamless and comfortable VR gameplay experience. Testing and iteration play a vital role in refining the VR experience, ensuring player comfort, and addressing any issues related to gameplay, comfort, and performance. Sound design enhances immersion, while multiplayer considerations add a social aspect to the virtual battlefield. By implementing cooperative gameplay, competitive modes, robust networking, and anti-cheat measures, developers can create engaging multiplayer experiences. Cross-platform support expands the player base and fosters a vibrant community. Continuous post-launch support, updates, and community engagement contribute to the long-term success of the game. With these stages and methods in mind, developers can embark on the exciting journey of FPS game development in virtual reality, crafting immersive and thrilling experiences for players to enjoy in the immersive VR world.

REFERENCES.

1. Lahti, J., Pärssinen, M., Laato, S., & Karkkainen, T. (2020). VR Game Development Challenges and Possibilities: Case Virtual Reality First Person Shooter. In 2020 3rd International Conference on Information and Computer Technologies (ICICT) (pp. 103-108). IEEE.
2. Israr, A., & Alam, M. (2021). Designing Virtual Reality Games: A Literature Review on Challenges, Considerations, and Solutions. In 2021 4th International Conference on Computer Applications & Information Security (ICCAIS) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

3. Mahrin, M. N., & Yahaya, S. A. (2020). A Review on Virtual Reality Game Development Challenges. *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, 15(5), 3317-3336.
4. Tanskanen, P., & Korhonen, H. (2019). Implementing Virtual Reality in Game Development Process. In *Proceedings of the 52nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*.
5. Mondejar, R., & Moreno-Ger, P. (2019). Virtual Reality in First Person Shooter Games: A Systematic Review. In *International Conference on Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, and Computer Graphics* (pp. 3-19). Springer.
6. Ibodullayev S.N, Bahromov A.A.(2020), ‘A variety of virtual reality implementations for creative learning and 5 ways to implement virtual reality in the learning process’, *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS)* ISSN: 2643-640X. Vol. 4, Issue 9.
7. Nuraliev F.M., Ibodullayev S.N,(2021), ‘Study of national heritage sites on the basis of gamification technology’, *International Conference On Information Science And Communications Technologies ICISCT 2021 Applications, Trends And Opportunities*, 3-5 November 2021, Tashkent Uzbekistan, <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9670083>.